

Quinoline Derivatives. Part IV.

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In nirvanine an acylamino group takes the place of usual benzoyloxy grouping of local anaesthetics. In percaine a similar grouping is noticeable and the ester grouping, so typical of this class of compounds, is missing. The basic part is a quinoline nucleus which can be the seat of local anaesthetic property (*cf.* Clemo and Perkin's tetrahydroquinolone, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **128**, 1608). Therefore it seemed of interest to prepare substance of the type (I).

These have been prepared by the hydrolysis of the *azlactones* of varatric aldehyde and piperonal to the acids (II). These are easily reduced

to the dihydro-acids (III), which as is usual with veratric aldehyde and piperonal derivatives nitrate in the 6-position (marked¹⁰) to give the corresponding 6-nitro-acids. These, on reduction, pass by simultaneous ring-closure to the 3-acylamminotetrahydroquinolones (I).

Attempts to prepare amidines (IV) were not successful.

In view of the fact that 3:4-dihydroxyphenylalanine has been isolated from velvet beans (Miller, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1920, **44**, 481) and the probability of substances of this type being the precursor of isoquinoline alkaloids in plants, we have prepared 3:4-methylenedioxyphenylalanine by the hydrolysis of (III). Dihydroxyphenylalanine has been previously prepared by Stephen and Weizmann (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 1152) by an indirect route.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

The azlactone (4 g.) from veratric aldehyde and hippuric acid, suspended in potassium hydroxide solution (35 c.c., 3%) was heated for 10 minutes till a complete solution resulted. The well cooled solution was just acidified with acetic acid and the precipitate was crystallised from dilute alcohol in silky needles, m.p. 208°, yield 3.8 g. (Found: N, 4.37. $C_{18}H_{17}O_5$ N requires N, 4.28 per cent). The substance (II, R = R' = OMe) is soluble in alkali carbonate solutions and reacts acid.

The foregoing acid (10 g.) was reduced with sodium amalgam (200 g., 2½ %) in a stoppered bottle with shaking and cooling. The alkaline solution furnished on acidification (III, R = R' = OMe). The crude product was dissolved in ether and extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution whence on reacidification the substance was precipitated and then crystallised from hot water, m. p. 158°. (Found: N, 4.34. $C_{18}H_{19}O_5$ N requires N, 4.34 per cent).

The above described acid (2 g.) in acetic acid (10 c.c.) containing 3 drops of sulphuric acid (d 1.84) was treated with nitric acid (d 1.52, 2 c.c.) diluted with acetic acid (2 c.c.) at 50°. The product after

standing for 15 minutes was poured on ice and the precipitate crystallised from alcohol in yellow silky needles, m. p. 208°, yield 1.1 g. (Found : N, 7.29. $C_{18}H_{18}O_7N_2$ requires N, 7.48 per cent).

A solution of foregoing β -6-nitro-3 : 4-dimethoxy- α -benzoylamino-phenylpropionic acid (1 g.) was reduced with hydrated ferrous sulphate (10 g.) in water (15 c.c.) at 100° with ammonia for 45 minutes, the loss of ammonia being made good by fresh addition. The clear filtrate was well cooled and acidified with acetic acid. The separated solids and the residue from ether extraction of the mother liquor were crystallised from hot dilute acetic acid, m. p. 225°, yield 0.2 g. The substance does not contain a diazotisable amino group. (Found : N, 8.63. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.59 per cent).

The azlactone from piperonal and hippuric acid (4 g.) was hydrolysed as described before with potassium hydroxide solution (35 c.c., 3%). After acidification with acetic acid, the separated solids were crystallised from hot acetic acid, m. p. 224°. (Found: N, 4.59. $C_{17}H_{13}O_5N$ requires N, 4.50 per cent). The above acid on reduction with sodium amalgam furnished a product (III, R, R' = $O_2 : CH_2$), m. p. 122° after crystallisation from alcohol.

On nitration of the acid (2 g.) in acetic acid solution as described before, the nitro-acid, m. p. 210°, was obtained in yellow silky needles (1.1 g.). (Found : N, 7.56. $C_{17}H_{14}O_7N_2$ requires N, 7.82 per cent).

The nitro-acid (1 g.) was reduced with hydrated ferrous sulphate (10 g.) as described before. The mother liquor after acidification was extracted with chloroform in this case and the product was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 254°, yield 0.2 g. (Found : N, 8.74. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.03 per cent).

Hydrolysis of β -3:4-Methylenedioxy- α -benzoylamino-phenylpropionic Acid to β -3 : 4-Methylenedioxyphenylalanine Hydrochloride.—The acid (III, R, R' = $O_2 : CH_2$) (1 g.) suspended in hydrochloric acid (d 1.16, 50 c.c.) was heated at 100° for 4 hours, a few c.c. of acetic acid being added to facilitate solution. Hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) was further added during the hydrolysis. The well cooled solution was extracted with ether and the aqueous portion then concentrated in a desiccator. The crystalline deposit of the amino-acid hydrochloride was collected, washed with ether and recrystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid, m. p. 278-80°, yield 0.1 g. (Found : N, 5.07; Cl, 13.1. $C_{10}H_{12}O_4NCl$, H_2O requires N, 5.31; Cl, 13.7 per cent.). The substance gave off water of crystallisation but it could not be satisfacto-

rily estimated owing to slight decomposition on prolonged heating at 120° .

The Anilide of 6-Nitro-3:4-methylenedioxy-cinnamic Acid.—6-Nitro-3:4-methylenedioxy-cinnamic acid (1 g.) was converted into its chloride in benzene solution with thionyl chloride. The solid acid chloride (without purification) was reacted with aniline in benzene solution. The anilide crystallised in needles from alcohol, m. p. 205° . (Found: N, 9.02. $C_{16}H_{12}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.97 per cent). On reduction this substance did not give the amidine as expected but was hydrolysed to 3:4-methylenedioxyquinolone, m. p. 205° . The structure was confirmed by synthesising the quinolone from 6-nitro-3:4-methylenedioxy-cinnamic acid by reduction as follows:—

1 G. of the 6-nitro-3:4-methylenedioxy-cinnamic acid dissolved in ammonia was reduced with ferrous sulphate (20 g.) in water (50 c.c.) on the steam-bath. The filtered solution on acidification gave the 3:4-methylenedioxyquinolone, m. p. 205° after crystallisation from alcohol. It does not contain a diazotisable amino or a carboxy group. (Found: N, 7.52. $C_{10}H_7O_3$ N requires N, 7.40 per cent).

Similarly β -3:4-methylenedioxy-6-nitrophenylpropionic acid (Ahluwalia, Kaul and Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 200) was converted into the chloride, which was then condensed with anthranilic acid in pyridine solution to β -3:4-methylenedioxy-6-nitrophenylpropionylanthranilic acid, m. p. 208° after crystallisation from acetic acid. (Found: N, 8.07. $C_{17}H_{14}O_7N_2$ requires N, 7.81 per cent). This substance also on reduction with ferrous sulphate in ammoniacal solution was hydrolysed to 3:4-methylenedioxytetrahydroquinolone (m. p. 232°), prepared for confirmation by the reduction of β -3:4-methylenedioxy-6-nitrophenylpropionic acid with ferrous sulphate, m. p. 232° (mixed m. p. 232° with above). (Found: N, 7.25. $C_{10}H_9O_3$ N requires N, 7.33 per cent). The substance had no acidic properties nor it had diazotisable amino group.

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